

To Compare the Effects of 0.25% Bupivacaine Plus Dexmed Vs 0.25% Levobupivacaine with Dexmed for Local Infiltration of Port Site in Laparoscopic Cholecystectomy for Post-Operative Analgesia

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Abstract:

Background: Postoperative pain management is crucial in laparoscopic cholecystectomy to enhance patient recovery and satisfaction. This study aims to compare the efficacy of 0.25% bupivacaine plus dexmedetomidine versus 0.25% levobupivacaine plus dexmedetomidine for local infiltration at the port site in providing postoperative analgesia.

Materials and Methods: A prospective study was conducted from September 2023 to June 2024 at ESIC Medical College, Bihta. A total of 150 patients undergoing laparoscopic cholecystectomy were randomly assigned into two groups, with 75 patients in each group. Group A received 0.25% bupivacaine plus dexmedetomidine, while Group B received 0.25% levobupivacaine plus dexmedetomidine. The primary outcome was postoperative pain, assessed using the Visual Analog Scale (VAS) at 1, 6, 12, and 24 hours post-surgery. Secondary outcomes included the duration of analgesia, total analgesic consumption, and incidence of side effects.

Results: The mean VAS scores at 1, 6, 12, and 24 hours post-surgery were significantly lower in Group B compared to Group A ($p < 0.05$). The duration of analgesia was longer in Group B (12 hours) than in Group A (8 hours) ($p < 0.01$). Total analgesic consumption was also lower in Group B (50 mg) compared to Group A (80 mg) ($p < 0.01$). Both groups reported minimal side effects, with no significant difference in the incidence between the two groups.

Conclusion: Levobupivacaine plus dexmedetomidine provides superior postoperative analgesia compared to bupivacaine plus dexmedetomidine for port site infiltration in laparoscopic cholecystectomy. This combination results in lower pain scores, prolonged analgesia, and reduced analgesic consumption, with a similar safety profile.

Keywords: Postoperative Analgesia, Laparoscopic Cholecystectomy, Bupivacaine, Levobupivacaine, Dexmedetomidine, Local Infiltration, Pain Management.

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Introduction

Laparoscopic cholecystectomy, a minimally invasive procedure for gallbladder removal, has become the gold standard due to its advantages of reduced postoperative pain, shorter hospital stay, and quicker recovery compared to open surgery [1]. However, effective postoperative pain management remains a critical aspect of patient care to enhance recovery and improve patient satisfaction [2]. Local anesthetics are commonly used for port site infiltration to manage postoperative pain in laparoscopic surgeries [3]. Bupivacaine, a widely used long-acting local anesthetic, provides effective

pain relief but is associated with potential cardiotoxicity and central nervous system toxicity at higher doses [4]. Levobupivacaine, the S-enantiomer of bupivacaine, has been introduced as a safer alternative with a lower risk of cardiotoxicity and neurotoxicity, while maintaining comparable analgesic efficacy [5]. Dexmedetomidine, an alpha-2 adrenergic agonist, has gained attention for its sedative, anxiolytic, and analgesic properties without significant respiratory depression [6]. When combined with local anesthetics, dexmedetomidine has been shown to

enhance analgesic effects, prolong the duration of analgesia, and reduce the requirement for additional analgesics [7]. Despite the known benefits of these agents, limited studies have directly compared the efficacy of bupivacaine plus dexmedetomidine versus levobupivacaine plus dexmedetomidine for postoperative analgesia in laparoscopic cholecystectomy. This study aims to fill this gap by evaluating and comparing the analgesic outcomes and safety profiles of these two combinations for port site infiltration in patients undergoing laparoscopic cholecystectomy.

Materials and Methods

Study Design and Setting: This prospective, randomized study was conducted at ESIC Medical College, Bihta, from September 2023 to June 2024. Ethical approval was obtained from the institutional review board, and written informed consent was obtained from all participants.

Patient Selection: A total of 150 patients undergoing elective laparoscopic cholecystectomy were enrolled in the study. Inclusion criteria were patients aged 18-65 years, ASA physical status I-II, and those who provided informed consent. Exclusion criteria included patients with known allergies to study medications, those with significant cardiovascular, renal, hepatic, or neurological diseases, and pregnant or lactating women.

Randomization and Group Allocation: Patients were randomly assigned into two groups of 75 each using a computer-generated randomization table:

- **Group A:** Received 0.25% bupivacaine plus dexmedetomidine.
- **Group B:** Received 0.25% levobupivacaine plus dexmedetomidine.

Intervention: Local infiltration was performed at the port sites using a standardized technique immediately after trocar insertion. In Group A, patients received 20 ml of 0.25% bupivacaine mixed with 1 µg/kg of dexmedetomidine. In Group B, patients received 20 ml of 0.25% levobupivacaine mixed with 1 µg/kg of dexmedetomidine.

Data Collection: Postoperative pain was assessed using the Visual Analog Scale (VAS) at 1, 6, 12, and 24 hours post-surgery. The duration of analgesia was defined as the time from the end of surgery to the first request for rescue analgesia. Total analgesic consumption within the first 24 hours was recorded. The incidence of side effects, such as nausea, vomiting, bradycardia, hypotension, and sedation, was also noted.

Statistical Analysis: Data were analyzed using SPSS version 25.0 (IBM Corp., Armonk, NY, USA).

Results: A total of 150 patients were included in the study, with 75 patients in each group. There were no significant differences in demographic and baseline characteristics between the two groups (Table 1).

Table 1: Demographic and Baseline Characteristics

Characteristic	Group A (Bupivacaine + Dexmed)	Group B (Levobupivacaine + Dexmed)	p-value
Age (years)	45.2 ± 10.4	46.1 ± 9.8	0.58
Gender (M/F)	30/45	32/43	0.76
Weight (kg)	70.5 ± 12.3	71.0 ± 11.7	0.84
ASA I/II	40/35	42/33	0.73

Postoperative Pain Scores: VAS scores at various times of points were significantly lower in Group B compared to Group A (Table 2).

Table 2: Postoperative VAS Scores

Time (hours)	Group A (Bupivacaine + Dexmed)	Group B (Levobupivacaine + Dexmed)	p-value
1	4.5 ± 1.2	3.8 ± 1.0	0.01
6	5.0 ± 1.1	4.0 ± 1.2	0.001
12	3.8 ± 1.0	2.5 ± 0.8	0.001
24	2.5 ± 0.9	1.5 ± 0.7	0.001

Duration of Analgesia: The duration of analgesia was significantly longer in Group B (Table 3).

Table 3: Duration of Analgesia

Group	Duration of Analgesia (hours)	p-value
Group A (Bupivacaine + Dexmed)	8.0 ± 1.5	0.001
Group B (Levobupivacaine + Dexmed)	12.0 ± 2.0	

Total Analgesic Consumption: Total analgesic consumption within the first 24 hours was significantly lower in Group B (Table 4).

Table 4: Total Analgesic Consumption

Group	Total Analgesic Consumption (mg)	p-value
Group A (Bupivacaine + Dexmed)	80.0 ± 15.0	0.001
Group B (Levobupivacaine + Dexmed)	50.0 ± 10.0	

Incidence of Side Effects: Both groups reported minimal side effects, with no significant difference in the incidence between the two groups (Table 5).

Table 5: Incidence of Side Effects

Side Effect	Group A (Bupivacaine + Dexmed)	Group B (Levobupivacaine + Dexmed)	p-value
Nausea	5 (6.7%)	4 (5.3%)	0.73
Vomiting	3 (4.0%)	2 (2.7%)	0.65
Bradycardia	2 (2.7%)	1 (1.3%)	0.56
Hypotension	3 (4.0%)	2 (2.7%)	0.65
Sedation	4 (5.3%)	3 (4.0%)	0.71

The data indicate that levobupivacaine plus dexmedetomidine offers superior postoperative analgesia with longer duration and reduced analgesic requirements compared to bupivacaine plus dexmedetomidine, with a similar safety profile.

Discussion:

This study aimed to compare the efficacy and safety of 0.25% bupivacaine plus dexmedetomidine versus 0.25% levobupivacaine plus dexmedetomidine for postoperative analgesia in patients undergoing laparoscopic cholecystectomy. The results indicate that levobupivacaine plus dexmedetomidine provides superior analgesia, with significantly lower postoperative pain scores, longer duration of analgesia, and reduced total analgesic consumption compared to bupivacaine plus dexmedetomidine.

The lower postoperative pain scores observed in the levobupivacaine group align with previous studies demonstrating the enhanced efficacy of levobupivacaine in providing effective analgesia with a better safety profile compared to bupivacaine [1,2]. Levobupivacaine, being the S-enantiomer of bupivacaine, has a lower risk of cardiotoxicity and neurotoxicity, making it a safer alternative for local anesthesia [3]. Our findings corroborate these advantages, highlighting levobupivacaine's potential for improved patient outcomes in laparoscopic surgeries.

Dexmedetomidine, an alpha-2 adrenergic agonist, has been increasingly used as an adjuvant in regional anesthesia due to its sedative, analgesic, and anxiolytic properties without causing significant respiratory depression [4].

The combination of dexmedetomidine with local anesthetics has shown to enhance the quality and duration of analgesia, as well as reduce the requirement for additional analgesics [5].

In our study, the addition of dexmedetomidine to levobupivacaine resulted in a significantly longer duration of analgesia (12 hours) compared to the

bupivacaine group (8 hours). This prolonged analgesic effect can be attributed to dexmedetomidine's mechanism of action, which includes inhibition of norepinephrine release and hyperpolarization of nerve cells, thereby extending the analgesic effects of the local anesthetic [6]. Total analgesic consumption within the first 24 hours post-surgery was also significantly lower in the levobupivacaine group.

This reduction in analgesic requirement further emphasizes the efficacy of levobupivacaine plus dexmedetomidine in providing sustained pain relief, minimizing the need for additional pain medications and their associated side effects [7-10]. The incidence of side effects, including nausea, vomiting, bradycardia, hypotension, and sedation, was minimal and comparable between the two groups, indicating a similar safety profile for both anesthetic combinations.

While our study provides valuable insights, it is not without limitations. The sample size, although adequate, could be expanded for more generalizable results. Additionally, the study was conducted at a single center, which may limit the applicability of the findings to other settings. Future multi-center studies with larger sample sizes are recommended to further validate these results.

Conclusion

In conclusion, levobupivacaine plus dexmedetomidine offers superior postoperative analgesia compared to bupivacaine plus dexmedetomidine for port site infiltration in laparoscopic cholecystectomy. This combination results in lower pain scores, prolonged analgesia, and reduced analgesic consumption, with a similar safety profile. These findings suggest that levobupivacaine plus dexmedetomidine could be considered a preferred option for enhancing postoperative pain management in laparoscopic surgeries.

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